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**The longicorn beetle tribe Cerambycini Latreille, 1802
(Coleoptera: Cerambycidae: Cerambycinae) in the fauna of Asia.
15. Notes on the morphology and taxonomy of some representatives
of the genera *Neocerambyx* J. Thomson, 1861, *Massicus* Pascoe, 1867,
and *Massirachys* Vitali, Gouverneur et Chemin, 2017,
with a new synonymy**

© A.I. Miroshnikov^{1, 2}

¹Russian Entomological Society, Krasnodar, Russia. E-mail: miroshnikov-ai@yandex.ru
²Sochi National Park, Moskovskaya str., 21, Sochi, Krasnodar Region 354002 Russia

Abstract. The following new synonymy is established: *Massirachys mariae* J. Thomson, 1878 = *Massicus subregularis* Schwarzer, 1931, **syn. n.** On the basis of this synonymy, the former species, hitherto known only from Borneo, is being recorded from Sumatra for the first time. The record of the large male of *Massicus* (with a body length of 70 mm), very similar to the holotype male of *Massicus valentinae* Miroshnikov, 2017, but differing from it by some features, is presented. It is assumed that these differences lie within the limits of the individual variability of *M. valentinae*, therefore the large male is preliminarily assigned to this species. Previously unknown differences between *Massicus regius* Miroshnikov, 2019 and a very similar *M. pascoei* (J. Thomson, 1867), with which it has been confused for a long time, are discovered. The critical remarks on the recent M. Lazarev's publication about some representatives of the tribe Cerambycini are presented. The previously established synonymy *Neocerambyx* J. Thomson, 1861 = *Bulbocerambyx* Lazarev, 2019 is confirmed. The insolency and contradictions of the findings and conclusions of this author are shown. Serious doubts about the differences between *Neocerambyx vitalisi* Pic, 1923 and *Neocerambyx elenae* Lazarev, 2019 are confirmed.

Key words: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, Cerambycini, new synonymy, new records, Peninsular Malaysia, Sumatra, Borneo.

**Жуки-дровосеки трибы Cerambycini Latreille, 1802
(Coleoptera: Cerambycidae: Cerambycinae) фауны Азии.
15. Заметки по морфологии и таксономии некоторых представителей
родов *Neocerambyx* J. Thomson, 1861, *Massicus* Pascoe, 1867
и *Massirachys* Vitali, Gouverneur et Chemin, 2017 с новой синонимией**

© А.И. Мирошников^{1, 2}

¹Русское энтомологическое общество, Краснодар, Россия. E-mail: miroshnikov-ai@yandex.ru
²Сочинский национальный парк, ул. Московская, 21, Сочи, Краснодарский край 354000 Россия

Резюме. Установлена следующая новая синонимия: *Massirachys mariae* J. Thomson, 1878 = *Massicus subregularis* Schwarzer, 1931, **syn. n.** На основании этой синонимии первый вид, до сих известный только с Борнео, впервые указан для Суматры. Отмечена находка крупного самца *Massicus* (с длиной тела 70 мм), очень сходного с голотипом, самцом *Massicus valentinae* Miroshnikov, 2017, но отличающегося от него некоторыми признаками. Предполагается, что эти отличия лежат в пределах индивидуальной изменчивости *M. valentinae*, в связи с чем крупный самец предварительно отнесен к данному виду. Обнаружены ранее неизвестные отличия *Massicus regius* Miroshnikov, 2019 от очень сходного *M. pascoei* (J. Thomson, 1867), с которым его смешивали долгое время. Приведены критические замечания по поводу недавней публикации М.А. Лазарева о некоторых представителях трибы Cerambycini. Подтверждена ранее установленная следующая синонимия: *Neocerambyx* J. Thomson, 1861 = *Bulbocerambyx* Lazarev, 2019. Показаны несостоятельность и противоречия выводов и заключений этого автора. Подтверждены серьезные сомнения в отличиях между *Neocerambyx vitalisi* Pic, 1923 и *Neocerambyx elenae* Lazarev, 2019.

Ключевые слова: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, Cerambycini, новая синонимия, новые находки, Западная Малайзия, Суматра, Борнео.

Introduction

In the course of the study of various material of Asian Cerambycini that I received lately, a new synonymy have been established, as well as the distribution area is expanded and some previously unknown diagnostic, morphological features are discovered for certain species.

In addition, the recent Lazarev's publication [2020] on some representatives of the tribe gave rise to doubts again, as before [Miroshnikov, 2020], in the findings and conclusions of this author.

The material treated in this work belongs to the following institutional and private collections:

MNHN – Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle (Paris, France);

SMF – Senckenberg Forschungsinstitut und Naturmuseum Frankfurt (Frankfurt am Main, Germany);

cAM – collection of Alexandr Miroshnikov (Krasnodar, Russia);

cDH – collection of Daniel Heffern (Houston, Texas, USA);

cPJ – collection of Philippe Jacquot (Montboucher-sur-Jabron, France).

Genus *Massirachys*

Vitali, Gouverneur et Chemin, 2017

Massirachys Vitali, Gouverneur et Chemin, 2017a: 54. Vitali et al., 2017b: 98.

Type species *Pachydissus mariae* J. Thomson, 1878, by original designation.

Massirachys mariae (J. Thomson, 1878)
(Figs 1–8)

Pachydissus mariae J. Thomson, 1878: 2 (type locality: Borneo (according to the original description and the label of the holotype)).

Aeolesthes mariae: Gahan, 1890: 253; Aurivillius, 1912: 47; Heffern, 2005: 15; Heffern, 2013: 9.

Massirachys mariae: Vitali et al., 2017a: 54.

Massicus subregularis Schwarzer, 1931: 60 (type locality: “Sumatra (?)” (according to the original description); “Sumatra” (according to the label of the holotype)), **syn. n.** Heffern, 2005: 16; Heffern, 2013: 10; Lazarev, 2019: 1195 (as *Neocerambyx subregularis*; erroneous combination); Miroshnikov, 2020: 76 (“most likely belongs to the genus *Massirachys*”).

Material. 1♂, holotype (MNHN) (photograph), “*Mariae* Th[omson] Type T. C. 34 30 Borneo”, “ex Musaeo James Thomson”, “Th[omson]. Type”, “C. J. Gahan vidit 1890”, “Museum Paris coll. J. Thomson Paris 1952”, “Holotype”; 1♂ (cDH) (Fig. 7), E Malaysia, Sabah, Trus Madi Mt., 22.03.2000 (local collector), “*Massirachys mariae* (Thomson), det. C. Holzschuh”; 1♀ (cDH) (Fig. 8), E Malaysia, Sabah, Sandakan – Pinangah, 18.03.2005 (local collector), “*Massirachys mariae* (Thomson), det. C. Holzschuh”; 1♂, holotype of *Massicus subregularis* Schwarzer, 1931 (SMF) (Fig. 1), “Sumatra”, “Mohnike [leg.]”, “Coll. E. Witte”, “*Massicus subregularis* Schwarzer, det. Schwarzer 1930, Typus”, “Typus [upperside], Col. 112 [underside]”, “Senckenberg-Museum, Frankfurt/Main [upperside], SMF C 112 [underside]” (Fig. 4), “The type specimen is restored by A. Miroshnikov in 2020”; “*Massirachys mariae* (J. Thomson, 1878) ♂ det. A. Miroshnikov 2020”; 1♀, paratype of *Massicus subregularis* Schwarzer, 1931 (SMF) (Fig. 2), “Sumatra”, “Mohnike [leg.]”, “Coll. E. Witte”, “439”, “*Massicus subregularis* Schwarzer, det. Schwarzer 1930, Paratypus”, “Paratypus [upperside], Col. 112a. [underside]”, “Senckenberg-Museum, Frankfurt/Main [upperside], SMF C 112a [underside]” (Fig. 5), “*Massirachys mariae* (J. Thomson, 1878) ♀ det. A. Miroshnikov 2020”; 1♀, paratype of *Massicus subregularis* Schwarzer, 1931 (SMF) (Fig. 3), “Midden O-Borneo, H.C. Siebers, 4.1.1925”, “*Massicus subregularis* Schwarzer, det. Schwarzer 1930, Paratypus”, “Paratypus [upperside], Col. 112b. [underside]”, “Senckenberg-Museum, Frankfurt/Main [upperside], SMF C 112b [underside]” (Fig. 6), “*Massirachys mariae* (J. Thomson, 1878) ♀ det. A. Miroshnikov 2020”.

Notes. I have recently noticed [Miroshnikov, 2020: 76] that “*Massicus subregularis* Schwarzer, 1931 and *M. philippensis* Hüdepohl, 1990 I have also studied only from photographs of the type specimens and their generic attribution, like that of the previous taxon (here refers to *Massicus venustus* (Pascoe, 1859). – *A.M.*), needs to be clarified, although *M. subregularis* most likely belongs to the genus *Massirachys* Vitali, Gouverneur et Chemin, 2017”.

Currently, through the courtesy of Dr Damir Kovac (SMF) and great help of Dr Dmitry Telnov (Natural History Museum, London, United Kingdom) and Dr Alexey Yu. Solodovnikov (Natural History Museum of Denmark

(University of Copenhagen), Copenhagen, Denmark), I was able to study the holotype (male) and two paratypes (both females) of *Massicus subregularis* (Figs 1–6).

These type specimens turned out not only belonging to the genus *Massirachys*, as I assumed earlier [Miroshnikov, 2020], but are in general morphologically identical to the holotype male of *Massirachys mariae*, as well as to two other specimens (male and female; Figs 7–8) of this species, kindly provided to me by Mr Daniel J. Heffern (Houston, Texas, USA).

In that way, *Massirachys mariae* (J. Thomson, 1878) = *Massicus subregularis* Schwarzer, 1931, **syn. n.**

Distribution. Until now, this species has only been known from Borneo [Thomson, 1878; Aurivillius, 1912; Heffern, 2013; Vitali et al., 2017a; Tavakilian, Chevillotte, 2020]. Based on the material studied and new synonymy, *Massirachys mariae* is being recorded here from Sumatra for the first time.

Genus *Massicus* Pascoe, 1867

Massicus Pascoe, 1867: 319 (name replacement for *Conothorax* J. Thomson, 1864, non Jeckel, 1854 (Curculionidae)).

Type species *Cerambyx pascoei* J. Thomson, 1857, by monotypy.

Massicus valentinae Miroshnikov, 2017
(Figs 9–20)

Massicus valentinae Miroshnikov, 2017: 224 (type locality: W Malaysia, Pahang, Cameron Highlands, Tanah Rata (according to the original description and the label of the holotype)). Miroshnikov, 2019: 277; Miroshnikov, 2020: 81; Lazarev, 2020: 124.

Neocerambyx valentinae: Lazarev, 2019: 1195 (erroneous combination).

Material. 1♂ (cPJ) (Fig. 9), W Malaysia, Pahang, Cameron Highlands, Jasar Mt., 05.1993 (Ph. Garreau leg.), “*Massicus valentinae* Miroshnikov, 2017 ♂ det. A. Miroshnikov 2020 [preliminary determination]”.

Morphological notes. This species was described from one male (Fig. 10) and one female with body lengths of 41.5 and 52.4 mm, respectively [Miroshnikov, 2017]. Subsequently, I have studied two more females, one of which has a body length of 61.5 mm [Miroshnikov, 2019].

Recently, Mr Philippe Jacquot (Montboucher-sur-Jabron, France) kindly provided me for study a very large male from Cameron Highlands, Western Malaysia (Fig. 9), similar to the male holotype of *M. valentinae* (Fig. 10), but almost 1.7 times as long as this (the body length is 70 mm, the humeral width is 16.5 mm).

Comparing that male with the holotype of *M. valentinae*, the following features become evident: the head with a longer longitudinal median groove between the upper lobes of the eyes; the antennae somewhat longer, antennomere 1 with a more strongly developed tooth externally at the apex, antennomeres 3 and 4 somewhat more strongly inflated apically, thereby antennomere 3 distinctly curved and noticeably extending beyond the elytral base; the pronotum less strongly convex on the disc, with a less dense recumbent light setae (probably abraded partly) between the wide longitudinal stripes; the sutural angle of the elytra is extended into a longer tooth; the prosternal process with a much sharper tubercle at the apex

Figs 1–8. *Massirachys mariae* (J. Thomson, 1878), habitus, dorsal view, and labels.
 1–6 – *Massicus subregularis* Schwarzger, 1931, **syn. n.**: 1, 4 – male, holotype, 2, 5 – female, paratype (Sumatra), 3, 6 – female, paratype (Borneo); 7–8 – male and female (Borneo).
 Рис. 1–8. *Massirachys mariae* (J. Thomson, 1878), общий вид сверху и этикетки.
 1–6 – *Massicus subregularis* Schwarzger, 1931, **syn. n.**: 1, 4 – самец, голотип, 2, 5 – самка, паратип (Суматра), 3, 6 – самка, паратип (Борнео); 7–8 – самец и самка (Борнео).

Figs 9–20. *Massicus valentinae* Miroshnikov, 2017, habitus, dorsal view, and genitalia.

9, 11, 13, 15, 17, 19 – large male (Cameron Highlands, Western Malaysia); 10, 12, 14, 16, 18, 20 – male, holotype; 11–12 – apical part of dorsal arc (of tergite IX), dorsal view; 13–14 – apical part of penis, ventral view; 15–16 – apical part of tegmen, ventral view; 17–18 – sternite VIII, dorsal view; 19–20 – apical part of tergite VIII, dorsal view.

Рис. 9–20. *Massicus valentinae* Miroshnikov, 2017, общий вид сверху и гениталии.

9, 11, 13, 15, 17, 19 – крупный самец с Камерон Хайлендс (нагорья Камерон, Западная Малайзия); 10, 12, 14, 16, 18, 20 – самец, голотип; 11–12 – верхняя часть дорсальной дуги (тергита IX) сверху; 13–14 – верхняя часть пениса снизу; 15–16 – верхняя часть тегмена снизу; 17–18 – стернит VIII сверху; 19–20 – верхняя часть тергита VIII сверху.

and a somewhat peculiar shape; both last (visible) sternite and tergite with a distinct emargination apically.

When comparing the genitalia (Figs 11–20), there are no clear differences between these males, only in the large male, tergite 8 is with a more distinct emargination apically, as in Fig. 19 (cf. Fig. 20), and sternite 8 with a somewhat peculiar shape at the apex, as in Fig. 17 (cf. Fig. 18) (but in the latter case this may be due to the fact that sternite 8 in the holotype is partly deformed at the apex). The genitalia illustrations of both males (Figs 11–20) are the same size for convenience of comparing them with each other.

In the females of *M. valentinae*, the degree of development of the tubercle at the apex of the prosternal process is approximately in an intermediate state between the holotype and the large male.

Given the great distinction in the body size of the considered males (and some traits of the females), the above differences are obviously an individual variability. Therefore, I have preliminarily identified here the large male as *M. valentinae*.

Massicus regius Miroshnikov, 2019

Massicus regius Miroshnikov, 2019: 270 (type locality: W Malaysia, Pahang, Cameron Highlands, Tanah Rata (according to the original description and the label of the holotype). Miroshnikov, 2020: 74, 81; Lazarev, 2020: 123.

Neocerambyx regius: Lazarev, 2019: 1195 (erroneous combination).

Previously examined type material see in Miroshnikov [2019].

Comparative material. *Massicus pascoei* (J. Thomson, 1867): 1♀ (cAM), Vietnam, Lam Dong Prov., Da Lat, 04.2019 (local collector); 1♀ (cPJ), China, SW Yunnan, Longchuan County, 1500 m, 05–08.2019 (local collector), “*Massicus pascoei* (Thomson, 1857)”.

Morphological notes. The original description [Miroshnikov, 2019] presented clear differences between *M. regius* and a very similar species – *M. pascoei* (J. Thomson, 1857), with which it has been mixed for a long time.

When examining a female of *M. pascoei* from Yunnan, China, kindly provided to me for study by Mr Philippe Jacquot, and a female from southern Vietnam, I became convinced of the stability of another important difference between *M. regius* and this species. In the Chinese and Vietnamese females, as in other specimens of *M. pascoei* that I studied earlier [Miroshnikov, 2019], the apical external angle of antennomere 5 bears a distinct denticle, while in the all type specimens of *M. regius* (including the females) this antennomere doesn't bear a denticle [Miroshnikov, 2020: 80, figs 38, 43]. In some females of *M. pascoei*, the denticle is sometimes very well-developed [Miroshnikov, 2020: 80, fig. 37].

Thus, in *M. pascoei*, the apical external angle of antennomeres 5–10 shows a sharp denticle, whereas in *M. regius* such denticle is developed only on antennomeres 6–10.

Genus *Neocerambyx* J. Thomson, 1861

Neocerambyx J. Thomson, 1861: 194.

Bulbocerambyx Lazarev, 2019: 1194.

Type species *Cerambyx paris* Wiedemann, 1821, by subsequent designation [Thomson, 1864].

Notes. I have recently synonymized the genus *Bulbocerambyx* Lazarev, 2019 with the genus *Neocerambyx* J. Thomson, 1861 [Miroshnikov, 2020]. This genus was established by Lazarev [2019] only on the basis of a single feature (the shape of male antennomeres 3–4) for the following four species: *Neocerambyx gigas* (J. Thomson, 1878), *N. grandis* Gahan, 1891, *N. katarinae* Holzschuh, 2009 and *N. vitalisi* Pic, 1923.

I have showed that Lazarev did not take into account the structure of the antennae of many other species and different variations of the swelling of their male antennomeres 3–4. However, in his next publication, this author [Lazarev, 2020] has ignored my comments and again, as usual, without a detailed comparative morphological analysis and any illustrations, has restored “*Bulbocerambyx*” by the following strange short wording: “The shape of 3rd antennal joint is also rather valuable and the genus *Bulbocerambyx* Lazarev, 2019 nom. rest. is quite real”. But my given questions posed earlier [Miroshnikov, 2020: 80–81], remained unanswered. Here I will not repeat them again, but to illustrate my point I will only show how male antennomeres 3–4 are arranged, in particular, in the holotypes of *Neocerambyx unicolor* (Gahan, 1906) and *Neocerambyx pubescens* Fisher, 1936. As can be seen from the photographs (Figs 23, 24), the shape of these antennomeres in both species is subidentical to the syntype male of *N. vitalisi* (Fig. 25). However, even these taxa were not included by Lazarev in his “*Bulbocerambyx*”. The number of similar examples could be increased.

I therefore continue to believe that *Bulbocerambyx* is the artificial genus and still stand by my opinion: *Neocerambyx* J. Thomson, 1861 = *Bulbocerambyx* Lazarev, 2019.

Lazarev [2019] was also unable to convince other authors [Li et al., 2020] of the validity of establishing his “*Bulbocerambyx*”.

With regard *Neocerambyx vitalisi* and *N. unicolor*, Lazarev [2020: 122–123] has noted that “The statement by Miroshnikov (2020: 80, without corresponding illustrations), that *Neocerambyx unicolor* “is very similar to *Bulbocerambyx vitalisi*, including the structure of these antennomeres” was out of the reality”. Without any doubt, this author had never seen the type specimens of *Neocerambyx vitalisi* and *N. unicolor* (Figs 21, 22, 24, 25). Otherwise, he would not have made such irresponsible remarks. In addition, Lazarev was very confused in the generic attribution of *N. vitalisi*, at the same time including this species in his “*Bulbocerambyx*” [Lazarev, 2020: 123], then in *Neocerambyx* [Lazarev, 2020: 124].

In general, according to the content of Lazarev's works [2019, 2020], it is impossible to understand on the basis of what specific material he builds his findings and conclusions. The complete absence of relevant photographs (except for the habitus of the holotype of *Neocerambyx elenae* heavily greased) in these publications makes even more all the reasoning of their author very difficult to perceive.

Regarding my comments on *Neocerambyx elenae* Lazarev, 2019 [Miroshnikov, 2020: 82], Lazarev [2020: 123] has presented the following frankly surprising conclusion: “Besides the idle speculations by Miroshnikov (2020)

Figs 21–25. Species of the *Neocerambyx* J. Thomson, 1861, males.
 21, 24 – holotype of *N. unicolor* (Gahan, 1906) (photographs by Luboš Dembický); 22, 25 – syntype of *N. vitalisi* Pic, 1923 (photographs by Gérard Chemin); 23 – holotype of *N. pubescens* Fisher, 1936 (photograph by Alexander Konstantinov). 21–22 – habitus, dorsal view; 23–25 – head, pronotum and antennomeres 1–4, dorsal view.

Рис. 21–25. *Neocerambyx* J. Thomson, 1861, самцы.

21, 24 – голотип *N. unicolor* (Gahan, 1906) (фотографии Л. Дембицкого); 22, 25 – синтип *N. vitalisi* Pic, 1923 (фотографии Ж. Шемена); 23 – голотип *N. pubescens* Fisher, 1936 (фотография А. Константинова). 21–22 – общий вид сверху; 23–25 – голова, переднеспинка и 1–4-й членики усиков сверху.

on the similarity of *Neocerambyx vitalisi* Pic, 1923 and *Neocerambyx elenae* Lazarev, 2019 was based on nothing. *N. elenae* is a very good species not close to any other". It should be immediately recalled here that this author [Lazarev, 2019] erroneously compared *N. elenae* with the only very dissimilar species – *N. atratulus* (Holzschuh, 2018). Lazarev [2020: 124], following my remarks about the strong similarity between *N. elenae* and *N. vitalisi*, has placed *N. elenae* in the *unicolor*-group of the genus *Neocerambyx* (sensu Miroshnikov [2020]) together with *N. vitalisi* and *N. unicolor*, in complete contrast to his own statement indicated above.

So far, I have not been able to find any clear differences between *N. vitalisi* and *N. elenae*, comparing the various females of the former (more than 15 specimens from different areas (including northern ones) of Laos and Vietnam) with the picture of the holotype of the latter species. Lazarev provided no morphological evidence for *N. elenae*, but claims that "*N. elenae* is a very good species not close to any other" (however he had previously assured [Lazarev, 2019: 1196] that his new species "is very close to *N. atratulus*"). In my opinion, it is unscientific. If researchers will follow Lazarev's example when establishing new taxa, then systematics will soon turn into complete chaos.

As long as this author will not present the clear differences between *N. vitalisi* and his "new" species, I will regard the latter as a very dubious taxon and retain my [Miroshnikov, 2020: 82] previously assumed synonymy *Neocerambyx vitalisi* Pic, 1923 = ?*Neocerambyx elenae* Lazarev, 2019.

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